

Optimal Surgeon Positioning during Open Colorectal Surgeries

Md. Tanweer Alam

MBBS, MS (General Surgery), F.M.A.S (Coimbatore), Department of General Surgery, Fatma Hospital, Purnea, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Md. Tanweer Alam

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Surgeon positioning during open colorectal surgeries is a critical factor influencing surgical efficiency, complication rates, surgeon fatigue, and patient outcomes. Despite the growing emphasis on surgical ergonomics, the impact of specific positioning strategies on clinical and postoperative outcomes remains underexplored. This study aims to evaluate the effect of different surgeon positions during open colorectal surgeries.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted, involving 182 patients undergoing open colorectal surgery. Surgeon positioning was categorized into four groups: right-side dominant standing, left-side dominant standing, seated, and alternating standing. Data on surgical time, intraoperative complications, surgeon fatigue, and patient recovery were collected. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with a p-value of <0.05 considered significant.

Results: The right-side dominant standing position was associated with the shortest mean surgical time (160 minutes) and the lowest complication rate (8%). Surgeons in this position reported the lowest fatigue scores (mean = 4.2), and patients had the shortest hospital stays (mean = 7.2 days). In contrast, the seated position had the longest surgical time (210 minutes), highest complication rate (20%), and highest fatigue scores (mean = 7.5).

Conclusion: The right-side dominant standing position is the optimal surgeon positioning during open colorectal surgeries, significantly enhancing surgical efficiency, reducing complications, and minimizing surgeon fatigue, leading to faster patient recovery.

Recommendations: Surgeons should be trained and encouraged to adopt the right-side dominant standing position during open colorectal surgeries to improve surgical outcomes. Further research is recommended to explore the long-term benefits of optimal surgeon positioning on the surgeon's health and career longevity.

Keywords: Colorectal Surgery, Surgeon Positioning, Surgical Ergonomics, Intraoperative Complications, Surgeon Fatigue, Patient Recovery.

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Introduction

Open colorectal surgeries are complex procedures that require precise coordination, ergonomic considerations, and optimal positioning of the surgical team to achieve the best patient outcomes. The positioning of the surgeon during these surgeries is a critical yet often overlooked factor that can significantly influence surgical efficiency, intraoperative complications, and postoperative recovery. While minimally invasive techniques have gained popularity, open surgeries remain essential for complex cases such as large tumors, inflammatory diseases, or emergencies where laparoscopic access is limited. Therefore, understanding the optimal positioning during open colorectal surgeries is vital to enhance surgical performance and patient care [1].

The right-side dominant standing position is traditionally favored by many surgeons due to its

ergonomic advantages, including better visualization of the surgical field and improved access to the operative site. This position allows the surgeon to maintain a balanced stance, reducing physical strain and enhancing precision during critical maneuvers [2]. However, the impact of this positioning on various clinical outcomes, such as surgical time, complication rates, and surgeon fatigue, remains underexplored in the literature. Previous studies have highlighted the importance of ergonomics in surgery, emphasizing how poor positioning can lead to musculoskeletal disorders among surgeons, affecting their career longevity and overall performance [3]. Thus, a comprehensive evaluation of surgeon positioning is necessary to optimize surgical practice and prevent long-term health issues among practitioners.

Moreover, surgeon fatigue is a growing concern in the surgical community, particularly in high-stress environments like colorectal surgery. Fatigue not only affects the surgeon's focus and dexterity but also increases the likelihood of errors, which can adversely impact patient outcomes [4]. The surgeon's positioning plays a pivotal role in mitigating fatigue, with ergonomic positions contributing to less physical stress and improved cognitive function during lengthy procedures. The link between surgeon positioning, intraoperative efficiency, and patient recovery times has significant implications for clinical protocols and training programs aimed at enhancing surgical ergonomics. Recent studies have also underscored the economic implications of surgical positioning. Faster surgical times and reduced complication rates translate into shorter hospital stays and lower healthcare costs, emphasizing the broader impact of optimal surgeon positioning on healthcare systems [5].

This study aimed at evaluating the preferred positioning of surgeons during open colorectal surgeries.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at a tertiary care hospital in Purnea, Bihar, which caters to a large population and is well-equipped for conducting major colorectal surgeries.

Participants: A total of 182 participants, including patients undergoing open colorectal surgery, were included in the study. The selection was based on specific criteria to ensure relevance and minimize variability in outcomes.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above undergoing open colorectal surgery.
- Patients with a confirmed diagnosis requiring open surgical intervention.
- Surgeons with at least three years of experience in performing colorectal surgeries.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with contraindications for surgery.

- Patients undergoing laparoscopic or minimally invasive colorectal surgeries.
- Surgeries performed by surgeons in training or those with less than three years of experience.

Bias: To minimize bias, the study employed random sampling of eligible surgeries and ensured that data collectors were blinded to the study objectives. Observer bias was reduced by using a standardized checklist for documenting the surgeon's positioning and associated outcomes.

Variables: The variables included surgeon positioning (standing, sitting, left-side dominant, right-side dominant), surgical time, intraoperative complications, surgeon fatigue, and patient outcomes.

Data Collection: Data were collected through direct observation of surgeries, recording surgeon positioning, surgical time, and intraoperative complications. Additional data were gathered from patient medical records regarding postoperative outcomes.

Procedure: The surgeries were observed by trained personnel who documented the positioning of the surgeon throughout the procedure. Each surgery was classified based on the surgeon's positioning, and the associated outcomes were noted. Data on patient demographics, surgical details, and postoperative recovery were also recorded.

Statistical Analysis: The data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data, and inferential statistics were applied to assess the relationship between surgeon positioning and surgical outcomes. Chi-square tests were used for categorical variables, and ANOVA was applied for continuous variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 182 patients undergoing open colorectal surgery were included in this study. The mean age of the patients was 56.8 years (SD = 12.4), with a male-to-female ratio of 1.3:1. The majority of the patients (65%) were diagnosed with colorectal cancer, followed by diverticulitis (20%), inflammatory bowel disease (10%), and other conditions (5%).

Table 1: Participant Demographics and Primary Diagnoses

Variable	Value
Total Participants	182
Mean Age (years)	56.8 ± 12.4
Gender Distribution	
Male	104 (57.1%)
Female	78 (42.9%)
Primary Diagnosis	

Colorectal Cancer	118 (65%)
Diverticulitis	36 (20%)
Inflammatory Bowel Disease	18 (10%)
Other	10 (5%)

The surgeries were categorized based on the surgeon's positioning during the procedure. The most common position was the standing right-side dominant position, observed in 45% of the surgeries.

Table 2: Distribution of Surgeon Positioning

Surgeon Position	Number of Surgeries	Percentage
Standing Right-Side Dominant	82	45%
Standing Left-Side Dominant	40	22%
Seated Position	36	20%
Alternating Standing (Right/Left)	24	13%

The analysis revealed that surgeon positioning had a significant impact on surgical outcomes. The mean surgical time for the right-side dominant standing position was the shortest, with a mean of 160 minutes (SD = 20), while the seated position had the longest mean surgical time of 210 minutes (SD = 25).

Table 3: Mean Surgical Time by Surgeon Position

Surgeon Position	Mean Surgical Time (minutes)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Standing Right-Side Dominant	160	20
Standing Left-Side Dominant	175	22
Seated Position	210	25
Alternating Standing (Right/Left)	185	18

The intraoperative complication rate was also analyzed across different surgeon positions. The right-side dominant standing position had the lowest complication rate (8%), while the seated position had the highest complication rate (20%).

Table 4: Intraoperative Complication Rates by Surgeon Position

Surgeon Position	Intraoperative Complications (%)
Standing Right-Side Dominant	8%
Standing Left-Side Dominant	12%
Seated Position	20%
Alternating Standing (Right/Left)	10%

Surgeon fatigue was assessed using a subjective scale, with higher scores indicating greater fatigue. Surgeons in the seated position reported the highest fatigue scores (mean = 7.5, SD = 1.2), while those in the right-side dominant standing position reported the lowest fatigue scores (mean = 4.2, SD = 1.0).

Table 5: Surgeon Fatigue Scores by Position

Surgeon Position	Mean Fatigue Score	Standard Deviation (SD)
Standing Right-Side Dominant	4.2	1.0
Standing Left-Side Dominant	5.0	1.1
Seated Position	7.5	1.2
Alternating Standing (Right/Left)	5.5	1.0

Postoperative outcomes, including length of hospital stay and recovery time, were also influenced by the surgeon's positioning. Patients operated on by surgeons in the right-side dominant standing position had the shortest hospital stay (mean = 7.2 days, SD = 1.5), while those operated on by surgeons in the seated position had the longest hospital stay (mean = 10.5 days, SD = 2.0).

Table 6: Length of Hospital Stay by Surgeon Position

Surgeon Position	Mean Length of Hospital Stay (days)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Standing Right-Side Dominant	7.2	1.5
Standing Left-Side Dominant	8.0	1.8
Seated Position	10.5	2.0
Alternating Standing (Right/Left)	8.5	1.7

Statistical analysis revealed significant differences in surgical time ($p < 0.01$), intraoperative complications ($p < 0.05$), surgeon fatigue ($p <$

0.01), and length of hospital stay ($p < 0.01$) across different surgeon positions. The right-side dominant standing position was associated with the

most favorable outcomes in terms of surgical efficiency, lower complication rates, reduced surgeon fatigue, and shorter hospital stays.

Discussion

The study evaluated the impact of surgeon positioning during open colorectal surgeries on surgical outcomes, including surgical time, complication rates, surgeon fatigue, and patient recovery. A total of 182 surgeries were observed, with the right-side dominant standing position being the most common (45%). The findings indicate that this position significantly influenced several critical factors associated with the success of colorectal surgeries.

The right-side dominant standing position was associated with the shortest mean surgical time (160 minutes), compared to the seated position, which had the longest mean time (210 minutes). This suggests that the right-side dominant position allows for better maneuverability and efficiency during surgery, likely due to improved ergonomic access and visibility of the surgical field. In terms of complications, the right-side dominant position also had the lowest intraoperative complication rate (8%), while the seated position had the highest (20%). This finding underscores that optimal positioning not only enhances the speed of surgery but also contributes to safer operative conditions, minimizing the risk of complications.

Surgeon fatigue scores varied significantly across different positions, with the lowest fatigue reported in the right-side dominant standing position (mean score of 4.2) and the highest in the seated position (mean score of 7.5). This highlights the physical strain associated with certain positions, indicating that a standing, dominant-side approach may reduce fatigue levels due to better posture and alignment during surgery. The reduced fatigue is crucial, as it directly impacts the surgeon's focus, precision, and overall performance, thereby influencing patient outcomes.

Patients operated on by surgeons in the right-side dominant standing position had the shortest hospital stays, averaging 7.2 days, compared to 10.5 days for those operated on by seated surgeons. This finding indicates that the right-side dominant position contributes to more efficient surgeries with fewer complications, which in turn facilitates faster patient recovery. The shorter recovery times suggest a direct link between optimal surgeon positioning and improved postoperative care, reducing hospital burden and enhancing patient satisfaction.

Overall, the study's results demonstrate that the right-side dominant standing position is optimal for colorectal surgeries, significantly enhancing surgical efficiency, minimizing complications,

reducing surgeon fatigue, and promoting quicker patient recovery. These findings support the recommendation for surgeons to adopt this positioning technique to improve operative outcomes and patient care quality. Future studies could further explore the long-term benefits of such positioning, including its impact on the surgeon's health and career longevity.

The effects of standardized patient positioning during laparoscopic colorectal surgery was studied, specifically analyzing contact pressure at the shoulder and the occurrence of intraoperative peripheral nerve injuries (IPNI). The study found that a standardized positioning protocol improved surgical safety by reducing nerve injuries, suggesting that careful patient positioning is critical for maintaining a safe surgical field [6].

A prospective cohort study compared positioning with shoulder braces to positioning on the foam mattress Pink Pad® during laparoscopic colorectal surgery. The study found that positioning with shoulder braces significantly increased the risk of postoperative peripheral neuropathy (PPN) compared to the Pink Pad®, emphasizing the need for careful positioning to reduce complications [7].

A study highlighted the importance of altering surgeon positioning based on specific anatomical challenges, such as in patients with situs inversus totalis (SIT). The modified positioning facilitated a successful laparoscopic hemicolectomy by adapting the surgeon's stance relative to the patient's altered anatomy, demonstrating that tailored positioning can improve surgical access and outcomes [8].

A study discussed the importance of the operating room setup, equipment arrangement, and patient positioning in single-incision laparoscopic colorectal procedures. They emphasized that optimizing these factors is crucial for overcoming challenges like instrument crowding and ensuring effective surgical access, enhancing the overall success of the procedures [9].

Research explored the role of patient positioning in minimally invasive surgery (MIS) compared to conventional methods. Their findings indicated that precise patient positioning is essential to avoid complications and enhance the success of MIS, which requires meticulous coordination between the surgical team [10].

Conclusion

The results of this study suggest that the right-side dominant standing position is the optimal position for surgeons during open colorectal surgeries. This position was associated with the shortest surgical time, lowest complication rates, and minimal surgeon fatigue, contributing to better patient outcomes. Further studies are recommended to

validate these findings in larger and more diverse populations.

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